

BODY IMAGE IN ASIAN AMERICAN FEMALE COLLEGE STUDENTS

by

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Abstract

Body image is the individual's perception of their own body. To better understand how body image may affect an individual's mental and/or physical health, it is important to identify the degree to which factors contribute to one's body image, specifically for female Asian Americans. This study aims to examine the relationship between body image, physical activity, disordered eating attitudes and behaviors, and social media consumption, in female Asian American college students.

Keywords

Body image; physical activity; disordered eating; social media

Introduction

Body Image in Asian Americans

Body image is how an individual perceives one's overall body. Tylka and Wood-Barcalow (2015) discussed that a positive body image means that the individual appreciates, accepts, and is satisfied with their overall body; "[the] most positive information is internalized and most negative information is rejected or reframed" (Tylka & Wood-Barcalow, 2015, p.121). On the other hand, an individual with a negative body image is often dissatisfied with their body, which may occur when the perceived body image does not match with his/her ideal body image (Coelho et al., 2015). Researchers have found that positive and negative body images are distinct from each other, such that individuals with a positive body image may not necessarily mean that they have low levels of negative body image, as they are not measured on the same continuum (Tylka & Wood-Barcalow, 2015) and are not mutually exclusive.

Researchers have offered different operationalizations of body image. In this study, we focus on (1) the individual's evaluation of their physical appearance (self-evaluative salience), and (2) motivation to change their physical appearance (motivational salience; Cash, 2004).

Problems That Arise from a Negative Body Image

Problems that may arise for individuals with a negative body image can include disordered eating, substance abuse, psychological health issues (e.g, insomnia and depression), low self-esteem, and low quality of life (Moehlecke et al., 2020; Pinkasavage, et al., 2015). Individuals with a negative body image may feel anxious when looking at their body appearance and feel embarrassed when being seen by others (Osumi et al.,

2014). The effects on body image may vary depending on how an individual associates their body image to their self-worth, self-esteem, and weight (Sabik et al., 2010).

Asian Americans Female College Students

The perceived ideal body type or beauty “standards” may vary among cultures. In a study conducted by Sabik et al. (2010), when Asian American women were asked to compare themselves to European American women, they were dissatisfied with some of the features that are related to specific race-related phenotypes. For example, Asian/Asian Americans are often more dissatisfied with their eyelids. Another study conducted by Fredrick et al. (2016) demonstrated that Asian American women reported higher body dissatisfaction with their face and eye appearance as compared to White women.

Physical Activity

Studies have shown that there is a relationship between physical activity and body image. In a study conducted by Portolese and Stoll (2012), they found that participants who have increased weightlifting exercises had a decrease in their body image concerns. Studies also found gender differences in the relationships between physical activity levels and body image (dissatisfactions). In a study with over 13,514 participants in Brazil, men with higher intensity levels of physical activity reported better body satisfaction, and both weight and body image dissatisfaction were associated with the decrease of physical activity among women (Coelho et al., 2015). Therefore, this study focuses on examining the relationships between body image and physical activity among women only.

Disordered Eating

Studies have shown that mindful eating may lead to positive body image (Webb et al., 2018). Mindful eating is when the individual presents non-judgmental awareness or

intentional awareness of the food. On the other hand, research has suggested that there is an association between a negative body image and disordered eating behaviors (Pinkasavage et al., 2015). Individuals who express disordered eating behaviors may experience weight gain, persistent feelings of sadness, and a decrease in general well-being (Pinkasavage et al., 2015).

Social Media Consumption

Social media may play a role in one's perception of what an ideal body looks like. Research has shown that social media usage may lead to higher body image concerns. Image-based platforms, such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, may have an even greater influence. For example, the "fitness inspiration" Instagram posts are intended to inspire viewers to increase their physical activity. However, it becomes problematic when it only portrays only one body type, suggesting that that is what the ideal body looks like (Prichard et al., 2020).

Purpose of Study and Research Question

This study aimed to examine if there are relationships between physical activity, social media consumption, body image, and disordered eating for Asian American female college students. The study examined the following research questions: 1) Is physical activity related to body image? 2) Is social media consumption related to body image? 3) Does social media consumption affect Asian American female college students' physical activity levels and disordered eating behaviors? Do their body image beliefs mediate these relationships?

Methods

Participants

The average age of the 1072 participants is 21.19 ($SD = 3.46$). Among the participants, 81.4% ($n = 873$) identified as Asian American, 10.9% ($n = 117$) biracial or multiracial with Asian heritage, 6.2% ($n = 66$) Asian nationals, and 1.5% ($n = 16$) Native Hawaiian/Pacific Islander. There were 29.8% ($n = 319$) Vietnamese, 25.9% ($n = 278$) Filipina/Filipino/Filipinx, 15.1% ($n = 162$) Chinese, 7% ($n = 75$) Korean, 4.7% ($n = 50$) Japanese, 2.8% ($n = 30$) Taiwanese, 2.7% ($n = 29$) Indian, 2.4% ($n = 26$) multi-ethnic, and 2% ($n = 21$) Cambodian. Most of the participants (74.7%, $n = 781$) were born in the United States and 25.3% ($n = 264$) were born outside of the United States. Looking at the participants' socioeconomic status growing up, there were 40.8% ($n = 436$) in middle class, 31.6% ($n = 338$) in lower-middle class, 15.5% ($n = 166$) in lower class, 11.7% ($n = 125$) in middle-upper class, and 0.4% ($n = 4$) in upper class. As for their current socioeconomic status, there are 45.4% ($n = 485$) in middle class, 26.9% ($n = 287$) in lower-middle class, 16.5% ($n = 176$) in middle-upper class, 10.9% ($n = 116$) in lower class, and 0.4% in upper class.

Table 1

Asian Ethnicities

	Frequency	Percentage
Cambodian	21	2.0
Chinese	162	15.5
Filipina/Filipino/Filipinx	278	26.6

Japanese	50	4.8
Indian	29	2.8
Korean	75	7.2
Taiwanese	30	2.9
Vietnamese	319	30.5
Multi-ethnic	26	2.5

When we asked participants whether they have sought or received any mental health services, 70% ($n = 748$) responded no, while 30% ($n = 321$) responded yes. For those who responded yes, there were several reasons as to why they sought mental health services. Some of these include depression (17.8%, $n = 56$), stress (11.8%, $n = 37$), anxiety (11.5%, $n = 36$), therapy or counseling (9.2%, $n = 29$), post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD; 3.8%, $n = 12$), grief (3.2%, $n = 10$), eating disorder (ED; 1.3%, $n = 4$), and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) or attention deficit disorder (ADD; 0.6%, $n = 2$). The remaining 40.8% ($n = 135$) of the participants had two or more of the listed reasons or other.

Table 2

Reasons for mental health services

	Frequency	Percentage
Depression, suicidal thoughts/attempts, or self-harm ideology	56	17.8
Anxiety or panic attacks	36	11.5

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Depression and anxiety	76	24.2
ADHD or ADD	2	.6
Grief	10	3.2
Therapy/counseling	29	9.2
Stress, feeling overwhelmed, lack of motivation, family/personal issues, etc.	37	11.8
PTSD or other trauma	12	3.8
Eating disorder	4	1.3
Depression with another issue (ADHD, family issues, PTSD, etc.)	6	1.9
Anxiety with another issue (stress, ADHD, autism, etc.)	8	2.5
Anxiety, depression, and another issue (anger, stress, etc.)	27	8.6
Others (robbery, schizophrenia, addiction, sexual/substance abuse, etc.)	11	3.5

Participants were also asked about their ED history. Eighty-eight-point three percent ($n = 944$) of participants responded “no,” while 11.7% ($n = 125$) responded “yes.” Of those who responded yes, some of the diagnoses include anorexia nervosa (AN; 27.5%, $n = 33$), bulimia nervosa (BN; 18.3%, $n = 22$), binge eating (16.7%, $n = 20$), anxiety or stress eating (3.3%, $n = 4$), orthorexia (3.3%, $n = 4$), body dysmorphia (2.5%, $n = 3$). The remaining 28.4% ($n = 39$) of the participants identified with 2 or more of the listed reasons or other. The average BMI (kg/m^2) was 21.78 ($SD = 2.74$, ranging from 15.79 to 29.47),

with 76.3% in the “normal” category, 12% “overweight,” and 9.5% “underweight.” Approximately 11% of the participants reported having an ED in the past (as assessed by a self-report question), but only one-fourth of them sought treatment.

Table 3*Eating disorder history or diagnosis*

	Frequency	Percentage
AN	33	27.5
BN	22	18.3
AN and BN	6	5
Binge eating	20	16.7
AN and binge eating	1	.8
BN and binge eating	4	3.3
Anxiety/stress eating, or overeating	4	3.3
Body dysmorphia	3	2.5
Orthorexia	4	3.3
Starving	2	1.7
Fasting	2	1.7
Underdiagnosed or other issues (food addiction, loss of appetite, or food avoidance)	19	15.8

Measures

Demographic and Background. We asked about the participant's age, educational status, gender and sexual orientation, race, ethnicity, generational status, the location of their birthplace, religion, socioeconomic status (childhood and current), etc. In addition, participants were asked about their mental health status, disordered eating behaviors, and whether they have sought professional help in the past.

Body Image. Participants' body image was assessed using the Appearance Schema Inventory-Revised (ASI-R). The 20-item ASI-R questionnaire is a 5-point Likert scale that includes statements such as, "strongly disagree," "mostly disagree," "neither agree or disagree," "mostly agree," and "strongly agree" (Cash, 2003). This questionnaire includes 2 subscales — self-evaluative salience and motivational salience. The self-evaluative salience looks at how the individual measures their self-worth based on their physical appearance, while motivational salience reveals how motivated the individual is to change their physical appearance (Cash, n.d.). No previous studies used ASI-R with Asian American college students. However, in a study that includes racially/ethnically diverse samples of college women (21% Asian), the Cronbach's alpha for self-evaluative salience was .84 and .71 for motivational salience (Quick & Byrd-Bredbenner, 2014). The Cronbach's alpha of the ASI-R in this study is .89, with .84 for self-evaluative salience and .83 for motivational salience, which suggests good internal consistency.

Physical Activity. To assess how physically active participants are, the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ) was used. The IPAQ consists of 27 questions with 5 domains that measure how much time an individual has spent in each activity for the past 7 days. These activities are often performed daily and can be job-

related, transportation, housework, recreation, the time spent sitting, etc. The total scores obtained from the questionnaire separate participants into 3 categories — low, moderate, and high. Participants placed in the “low” category means that little to no physical activity was reported, “moderate” means they have exercised for at least 3-5 days, and “high” means the individuals have been active for 7 days (Booth, 2000). Given the total scores are additive, an internal reliability test is not available for this instrument. There were only two participants who were classified as “high activity level”, therefore, the high activity levels group was removed from the analysis.

Disordered Eating. To assess the participant’s disordered eating attitudes and behavior, the Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26) was used. The EAT-26 consists of 26 items, and it measures each item with a scale using “never,” “rarely,” “sometimes,” “often,” and “always” (Garner et al., 1982). A low score may indicate that the individual presents an eating problem. However, this test does not indicate whether the individual has an eating disorder. Studies conducted with Asian American and South Asian female college students had Cronbach's alpha ranging from .87 and .91 (Jennings et al., 2005; Khaled et al., 2018; Sahi Iyer & Haslam, 2003). The Cronbach’s alpha of the EAT-26 in this study is .83 (dieting = .81; bulimia = .77; oral control = .62). The overall Cronbach’s alpha(α) is above .70, which suggests good internal consistency. Since the oral control subscale has a score of .62, it means that the results from this subscale must be reviewed with caution. This study suggests that it is appropriate to use the overall EAT-26 scale, rather than individual subscales, due to its excellent reliability score.

Social Media Consumption. To determine how frequently participants consume YouTube, TikTok, and Instagram, we developed questions for this study. The responses

include more than once daily, once daily, 2-3 times a week, 4-5 times a week, once a week, and less than once a week.

Procedures

After receiving the University IRB approval, participants were recruited via email, social media (i.e. Facebook and Instagram), and other personal and professional networks (i.e. student clubs, email lists, Discord chat rooms, etc.). An email invitation was also sent to all self-identified Asian/Asian American college students at a large public university on the west coast. The eligibility criteria to participate were (1) over the age of 18, (2) identified as someone of Asian descent, (3) currently enrolled in a 4-year college or university, and (4) identified as female. Data were collected anonymously online through Qualtrics, a secure online data collection platform. There were 8 cash prizes (\$25 each) as incentives for participants to complete the survey. Participants were given an option to enter their email addresses in a separate database that is not connected to the research survey after they completed the study to be entered into the cash prize drawing. The survey was opened from October 14, 2020, to December 15, 2020.

Results

Physical Activity and Body Image.

An independent sample t-test was conducted to examine whether there were differences in Asian American female college students' body image to their levels of physical activity. The high activity levels group was removed from the analysis due to the small group size ($n = 2$). Results suggested that there was a significant relationship between levels of physical activity and body image beliefs regarding motivational salience, $t(994) = -3.48, p = .001$. However, the relationship between physical activity and self-evaluative salience body image was not significant, $p = .65$. Those in the moderate activity level group

reported having significantly higher levels of motivational salience ($\bar{x} = 3.71$) than those in the low activity level group ($\bar{x} = 3.52$). The overall results suggest that Asian American female college students with a moderate level of physical activity reported more motivation to change their physical appearance (motivational salience) compared to participants in the low level of physical activity category. However, there was no difference in how much they tied their physical appearance and their self-worth (self-evaluative salience) between the two groups.

Social Media and Body Image

A correlation test was performed to examine the relationship between social media consumption and body image. Results revealed that TikTok and Instagram consumptions, $r = .20, p < .001$; $r = .14, p < .001$ respectively, were statistically associated with overall body image beliefs. There were also significant associations with specific aspects of body image (self-evaluative salience $p < .001$ and motivational salience $p < .001$). However, there were no relationships between overall or specific components of body image and YouTube consumption. These results suggest that Asian American female college students who used TikTok and Instagram more frequently were more likely to tie their self-worth to their physical appearance and that they were more motivated to change their physical appearance.

Social Media, Physical Activity, Body Image, and Disordered Eating

Several path analyses were performed to answer the third research question: does social media consumption affect Asian American female college students' physical activity and disordered eating? Do their body image beliefs mediate these relationships?

See Figure 1 below that illustrates the conceptual mediation model.

Figure 1

Three path analyses were conducted to examine if body image mediated the relationship between social media, physical activity, and disordered eating (one analysis for each social media platform).

YouTube

Figure 2 illustrates the results for YouTube, which show that YouTube consumption does not significantly contribute to an individual's physical activity levels while it does contribute positively to their disordered eating behavior ($\beta = .07$). In other words, high YouTube consumption contributed to disordered eating for Asian American female college students. Next, body image was added to the path analyses as the mediator (see Figure 3). The results from this path analysis show that body image significantly contributes to physical activity levels ($\beta = .07$) and disordered eating behavior ($\beta = .45$). However, YouTube consumption does not contribute to body image beliefs ($\beta = .08$). Therefore, body image beliefs do not mediate the effects YouTube consumptions have on disordered eating.

Figure 2

Figure 3

TikTok

A path analysis was conducted to examine if body image mediated the relationship between TikTok, physical activity, and disordered eating behavior. First, the results (as shown in Figure 4) showed that TikTok significantly contributed to disordered eating ($\beta = .08$), while it does not to physical activity. With body image as the mediator, the results (as shown in Figure 5) showed that TikTok has a direct contribution to body image ($\beta = .20$), which then contributed to disordered eating ($\beta = .44$). Furthermore, the direct effects

of TikTok on disordered eating are no longer significant. Thus, body image has a complete mediation effect on the effects of TikTok on disordered eating. In other words, the effects TikTok has on disordered eating on Asian American female college students are primarily through their body image beliefs. Outside of body image beliefs, TikTok does not contribute to disordered eating behaviors.

Figure 4

Figure 5

Instagram

Lastly, a third path analysis was performed to examine if body image mediates the relationship between Instagram, physical activity, and disordered eating. Results revealed that Instagram does not significantly contribute to disordered eating or physical activity (as shown in Figure 6). With the addition of body image in the path analyses (as shown in Figure 7), results indicated that body image contributes to disordered eating significantly ($\beta = .45$) and Instagram contributes to body image significantly ($\beta = .14$) as well. Interestingly, when considering the mediating effect of body image, Instagram's direct contribution to disordered eating became an inverse one ($\beta = -.07$). In other words, although Instagram does not have a direct impact on Asian American female college students' disordered eating behavior directly, it has a significant impact on disordered eating through its contribution to body image. More specifically, higher Instagram consumption leads to higher salience overall (using body image as the basis of self-worth and the motivation to change one's appearance), which leads to more disordered eating beliefs and behaviors. It should be noted that outside of the effects through body image, higher Instagram consumption was found to lead to less disordered eating behaviors and beliefs.

Figure 6

Figure 7

Discussion

There are very few studies on the relationship between physical activity and body image, especially among Asian American female college students. College students are especially vulnerable to body image issues and concerns as they are in the developmental stage where many are attempting to form their self-concept. Previous studies have established that physical activity can improve an individual's mental health outcome (Paluska & Schwenk, 2000), however, it was unclear if physical activity is the outcome or contributor of body image for Asian American female college students. This study found that a moderate level of physical activity was associated with more motivational salience (i.e., more motivation to change one's appearance) compared to a low level of physical activity, but not self-evaluative (i.e., self-worth is tied to appearance). Our study only compared moderate-level and low-level physical activity due to the very small sample size of those who engaged in high-intensity levels. It is consistent with previous literature that the prevalence of high and moderate-intensity physical activity is low, especially the high-intensity level among women (Coelho et al., 2015). Therefore, it may be helpful to

encourage Asian American female college students to engage in physical activity because of the positive relationships with mental health and to focus on creating a variety of moderate-level activities instead of high-intensity ones.

This study also examined if consumption of various social media platforms related to body image differently. Previous studies have found a relationship between social media consumption (e.g., Facebook, YouTube, Instagram) and body image in young adult women (see review by Perloff, 2014). Results from this study specifically examined YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok and their relationships with body image. Our results indicated that while TikTok and Instagram consumption is statistically significantly related to body image, YouTube consumption does not. In past studies, some researchers examined the “fitspiration” movement on YouTube and found that the Fitness YouTubers tend to promote unhealthy behaviors to achieve fitness, and the top comments typically expressed beliefs in and replication of their advice (Ratwatte & Mattacola, 2019). There may be a few factors why our current study did not find YouTube to be associated with body image. First, this study directly assessed the amount of social media consumption, rather than analyzing the top comments to a specific type of videos on YouTube or interviewing participants at a qualitative level. In addition, in recent years, there has been a rise in popularity in other social media platforms, such as Instagram and TikTok, which may lead to a decrease in usage in YouTube. Lastly, YouTube currently may be used more often for other purposes with the emergence of other social media platforms, such as self-help, education, or entertainment.

This is the first study that we know of that examined if body image mediated the relationships between social media consumption and physical activity and disordered

eating. Our results revealed that body image had a complete mediating effect on the relationship between TikTok and disordered eating, and it was a suppressor mediator for the relationship between Instagram and disordered eating. However, it does not have a mediating effect on the impact of YouTube on disordered eating. Recent studies have shown that Mukbang videos from YouTube can influence an individual's disordered eating behavior (Strand & Gustafsson, 2020). Mukbang videos consist of the host consuming a large portion of food while streaming or recording themselves then posting them on YouTube or other social media platforms. The study conducted by Strand and Gustafsson (2020) showed that both the participants and viewers of Mukbang videos were influenced by them but in a different manner. Some viewers found Mukbang videos help them maintain a restrictive diet and YouTube content creators creating Mukbang videos increased their food intake, which is also a form of disordered eating behaviors.

The results from this study had similar findings in that YouTube has a significant direct impact on disordered eating behavior and beliefs, however, it did not contribute to one's body image or physical activity level. This study found that body image had a complete mediation effect on the influence of TikTok on disordered eating, suggesting that most of the impact TikTok has on disordered eating is through its contribution to body image. Since the start of the COVID-19 pandemic in March 2020, there has been a rise in the popularity of such social media platforms, due to their convenience in allowing users to share their ideas or information across the world. Its main target audience is teens and young adults. The results from this study suggest that body image contributes to disordered eating behavior and TikTok contributes to body image. Recent studies that have examined the relationship between TikTok and body image also support this idea. Lin (2021)

suggests that TikTok accelerates the behavior of society's bias against the value of body types (i.e. having the "perfect body" rather than considering the individual's personality). With over one billion active users on the platform monthly, as of September 2021 (Reuters, 2021), this problem with body image can be concerning. Based on the findings from this study, it can be assumed that the removal of TikTok usage may help decrease body image issues, which can potentially decrease disordered eating behaviors.

Lastly, results of this study revealed that while Instagram does not have direct impacts on physical activity nor disordered eating, when considering body image as a mediating factor (e.g. outside the effects Instagram has on body image and in turn disordered eating), Instagram consumption itself contributes to *less* disordered eating behaviors and beliefs. Previously, studies have found that engagement in Instagram posts can lead to greater thin-ideal internalization, which has negative impacts on body image (Clark & Tiggemann, 2008; Cohen et al., 2017). A systematic review conducted by Holland and Tiggemann (2016) further suggests that there is a causal relationship between social networking sites (SNS), including Instagram, and disordered eating. However, past studies that found Instagram contributing to disordered eating may have missed an important factor that is the key to the relationship between Instagram and disordered eating. It is body image that's contributing to disordered eating, rather than Instagram consumption itself. Therefore, interventions should focus on addressing the connection between body image and Instagram consumption to combat mental health and disordered eating consequences.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

Results from this study contributed to a significant understanding of the relationships between social consumption, body image, physical activities, and body

image. However, there were also a few limitations to this study. First, the survey was only accessible to those who were comfortable with answering questionnaires in English online. Future research should consider offering similar surveys in multiple languages. The study was quantitative. Future research should consider qualitative interviews to explore other factors that contribute to female Asian American college students' body image in-depth and how social media consumption may play a role. This study used the short version of IPAQ to evaluate physical activity during leisure time and did not assess the level of activity during work or commute. Future research may consider measuring physical activities in different domains or the long version of IPAQ to conduct a more holistic assessment.

Conclusion

Studies on body image in Asian American female college students remain limited and this study offered some insights into the relationships between social media consumption, body image, physical activity, and disordered eating. Previously, most believed that social media consumption (e.g., Instagram) significantly contributes to women's disordered eating. However, results from this study revealed that negative body image beliefs played an important role in mediating the effects of social media on Asian American female college students' disordered eating. Furthermore, this study also showed that different social media platforms have different impacts on disordered eating and how they can be mediated by body image beliefs. An important finding is the effects of YouTube on disordered eating were not the same as studies conducted just a few years ago (Ratwatte & Mattacola, 2019). One possible explanation is that our study focused on Asian American female college students. However, another factor could be that the primary

content of social media platforms may evolve quickly even just in a couple of years. Therefore, rather than focusing on changing social media consumption habits or targeting certain platforms as problematic, results from this study highlighted the need to focus on individual psychological constructs, such as body image beliefs, as the mediating factor that filters the effects of social media on disordered eating.

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